

Fusion oncogenes in patients with locally advanced or distant metastatic differentiated thyroid cancer

Gaoda Ju^{1,2,3,4#}, Yuqing Sun^{2,3#}, Hao Wang⁵, Xin Zhang^{2,3}, Zhuanzhuan Mu^{2,3}, Di Sun^{2,3}, Lisha Huang⁶, Ruijue Lin⁷, Tao Xing¹, Wuying Cheng^{2,3}, Jun Liang^{1,4*}, Yan-Song Lin^{2,3*}

Supplementary files

Table S1. Genetic alterations and clinical characteristics of patients.

Table S2. Sequencing coverage and quality statistics of targeted NGS.

Table S3. Univariate and multivariate logistic regression analyses were used to evaluate the associations of N stage with the major genetic alterations.

Table S4. Difference in RAI-refractoriness between patients with RET-NCOA4 and patients with RET-CCDC6.

Figure S1. Age of patients with RET-NCOA4 and patients with RET-CCDC6.

Figure S2. NIS expression between WT PTC, PTC with BRAF mutation, and PTC with fusions.

Figure S3. The proportion of RAI-refractoriness in the Fusions group and the TERT mutation group.

Table S1. Genetic alterations and clinical characteristics of patients.

sampleID	RAI-refractoriness	HGVS	Age	Gender	Histopathologic type	AJCC_T	AJCC_N	AJCC_M
NGS220103-506	0	NCOA4 exon7-RET exon12	26.53150685	Male	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS211205-522	1	GOLGA5 exon7-RET exon12	50.72876712	Male	PTC	4a	1b	na
NGS210928-522	0	CCDC6 exon1-RET exon12	38.20273973	Female	PTC	1a	1b	0
NGS210315-203	0	NCOA4 exon7-RET exon12	22.55068493	Female	PTC	3b	1b	1
NGS211220-513	1	NCOA4 exon7-RET exon11	29.87123288	Female	PTC	3b	1b	1
NGS220130-510	0	NCOA4 exon7-RET exon12	25.2109589	Male	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS210507-100	0	NCOA4 exon6-RET exon12	11.15616438	Male	PTC	1a	1b	0

NGS210313-204	0	CCDC6 exon1-RET exon12	14.54520548	Female	PTC	1b	1b	0
NGS201223-064	0	CCDC6 exon2-RET exon11	37.15616438	Male	PTC	1b	1b	1
NGS210525-205	1	NCOA4 exon7-RET exon12	11.95068493	Female	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS201223-065	1	NCOA4 exon7-RET exon11	21.37808219	Female	PTC	4a	1b	0
NGS210724-514	0	TRIM33 exon14-RET exon12	16.2739726	Female	PTC	2	1b	1
NGS210315-206	0	TRIM27 exon3-RET exon12	16.83835616	Female	PTC	3b	1b	1
NGS220125-507	1	CCDC6 exon1-RET exon12	12.55068493	Female	PTC	na	1b	1
NGS211024-502	0	CCDC6 exon1-RET exon12	15.89589041	Female	PTC	1b	1b	0
NGS210702-503	0	NCOA4 exon7-RET exon12	5.879452055	Male	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS210928-515	1	ERC1 exon7-RET exon12	48.69315068	Female	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS220125-505	1	NCOA4 exon7-RET exon12	8.77260274	Male	PTC	1a	1b	1
NGS211121-513	0	GOLGA5 exon7-RET exon12	15.90958904	Female	PTC	1b	1b	1
NGS210419-102	1	CCDC6 exon1-RET exon12	8.978082192	Male	PTC	2	1b	1
NGS210808-511	0	CCDC6 exon1-RET exon12	17.0739726	Male	PTC	1a	1b	0
NGS210808-501	0	ERC1 exon7-RET exon12	25.1890411	Male	PTC	3b	1b	1
NGS211205-511	1	CCDC6 exon1-RET exon11	29.90410959	Female	PTC	2	1b	1
NGS211231-515	0	CCDC6 exon1-RET exon12	40.55890411	Male	PTC	1b	1b	1
NGS201223-077	1	CCDC6 exon2-RET exon11	30.71506849	Male	PTC	2	1b	1
NGS210329-119	1	CCDC6 exon1-RET exon12	52.79452055	Female	PDTC	4a	1b	1
NGS210801-509	0	CCDC6 exon1-RET exon12	39.54246575	Female	PTC	1a	1b	1
NGS210520-206	0	NCOA4 exon7-RET exon12	13.19452055	Female	PTC	2	1b	1
NGS210611-207	1	ERC1 exon7-RET exon12	65.60273973	Female	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS211121-515	0	NCOA4 exon7-RET exon12	46.21917808	Male	PTC	3b	1b	1
NGS201223-063	0	NCOA4 exon7-NCOA4 exon8-RET exon11	55.19178082	Female	PTC	na	1b	1
NGS211231-505	1	ERC1 exon13-RET exon12	45.06575342	Female	PTC	1b	1b	1
NGS210823-504	1	CCDC6 exon1-RET exon12	26.90958904	Male	PTC	2	1b	1
NGS211231-501	0	CCDC6 exon1-RET exon12	9.320547945	Male	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS211220-518	0	CCDC6 exon1-RET exon12	52.15342466	Male	PTC	1b	1b	0
NGS210624-205	0	NCOA4 exon8-RET exon11	24.64109589	Female	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS211205-509	0	CCDC6 exon1-RET exon12	36.42191781	Male	PTC	1b	1b	1
NGS201223-075	0	TRIM27 exon3-RET exon11	38.26849315	Male	PTC	1a	na	1
NGS211220-520	0	NCOA4 exon7-RET exon12	34.39452055	Male	PTC	1b	1b	1
NGS211024-513	1	LMNA exon2-RET exon12	19.18356164	Male	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS201223-074	0	NCOA4 exon8-RET exon11	34.85479452	Male	PTC	4a	1b	1

NGS210315-204	1	NCOA4 exon7-RET exon12	16.90136986	Male	PTC	3b	1b	1
NGS210702-505	0	CCDC6 exon1-RET exon12	11.01643836	Female	PTC	3a	1b	0
NGS210520-203	1	NCOA4 exon7-RET exon12	7.073972603	Male	PTC	3b	1b	1
NGS210210-071	1	CCDC6 exon1-RET exon12	30.16986301	Female	PTC	2	1b	1
NGS211220-515	0	NCOA4 exon7-RET exon12	31.02739726	Female	PTC	1a	1b	1
NGS210904-510	0	CCDC6 exon1-RET exon12	67.14246575	Female	PTC	2	1b	0
NGS210823-509	0	NCOA4 exon7-RET exon12	13.88219178	Female	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS211205-505	1	NCOA4 exon7-RET exon11	27.35890411	Female	PTC	1b	1b	1
NGS211220-517	0	CCDC6 exon1-RET exon12	30.44109589	Female	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS201228-060	0	NCOA4 exon7-RET exon11	50.74246575	Male	PTC	1a	1b	1
NGS210801-504	0	NCOA4 exon7-RET exon12	30.29315068	Male	PTC	1b	1b	1
NGS211121-504	0	NCOA4 exon7-RET exon11	22.70410959	Female	PTC	2	1b	1
NGS211028-503	0	NCOA4 exon7-RET exon12	23.17260274	Male	PTC	3b	1b	1
NGS210904-505	0	CCDC6 exon1-RET exon12	11.16712329	Male	PTC	1b	1b	1
NGS220125-513	0	CCDC6 exon1-RET exon12	23.99178082	Female	PTC	2	1b	1
NGS211024-512	0	CCDC6 exon1-RET exon12	42.92876712	Male	PTC	1b	1a	1
NGS210724-506	1	NCOA4 exon7-RET exon12	12.14520548	Male	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS210117-138	1	NCOA4 exon6-RET exon11	30.71506849	Male	PTC	2	1b	1
NGS220125-501	0	CCDC6 exon8-RET exon12	31.2109589	Female	PTC	1b	1b	0
NGS211205-508	1	CCDC6 exon1-RET exon12	67.18356164	Female	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS210801-511	0	TPR exon9-RET exon12	33.00547945	Female	PTC	1b	1b	1
NGS210808-504	1	NCOA4 exon7-RET exon12	14.83835616	Male	PTC	2	1b	1
NGS211205-515	1	NCOA4 exon7-RET exon12	42.97808219	Male	PTC	1a	1b	1
NGS210808-508	1	NCOA4 exon7-RET exon12	28.13424658	Female	PTC	1b	1b	1
NGS211121-508	0	ERC1 exon8-RET exon12	28.98630137	Female	PTC	3b	1b	1
NGS210823-506	0	NCOA4 exon7-RET exon12	22.23013699	Female	PTC	2	1b	1
NGS220228-501	1	CCDC6 exon1-RET exon12	25.9260274	Female	PTC	na	1b	1
NGS220103-510	0	NCOA4 exon7-RET exon11	8.323287671	Female	PTC	3b	1b	1
NGS210605-206	1	.	51.65205479	Male	FTC	3a	x	1
NGS210702-501	1	.	47.79452055	Male	PTC	4a	1a	1
NGS210329-103	1	.	30.28767123	Female	PTC	4b	1b	1
NGS210117-135	1	.	35.68767123	Female	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS210322-207	1	.	46.24657534	Female	PTC	na	1b	1
NGS210928-523	1	.	42.6739726	Female	PTC	3b	1b	1
NGS210303-033	0	.	35.81917808	Female	PTC	2	na	1

NGS210329-115	1	.		47.58630137	Male	PTC	1b	1b	1
NGS220103-513	0	.		32.78356164	Male	PTC	4a	1b	0
NGS211231-503	1	.		39.88493151	Female	FTC	na	na	1
NGS210405-201	1	.		41.86575342	Female	PTC	2	1b	1
NGS210928-507	1	.		35.41369863	Female	PTC	1a	1b	1
NGS211028-507	1	.		34.76986301	Female	FTC	na	na	1
NGS211121-507	0	.		5.060273973	Male	PTC	3b	1b	0
NGS210814-501	0	.		49.85753425	Male	PTC	1a	1b	1
NGS210611-201	0	.		33.84657534	Female	PTC	1b	1a	1
NGS210928-520	0	.		27.99178082	Male	PTC	1b	1a	0
NGS210520-202	1	.		46.09863014	Male	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS210904-506	1	.		56.89589041	Female	PTC	1a	1b	1
NGS210313-205	1	.		54.91232877	Female	FTC	x	0	1
NGS210801-510	0	.		17.02465753	Male	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS201228-061	1	.		81.36164384	Male	PTC	2	1b	1
NGS210205-080	1	.		18.19726027	Female	PTC	1b	1b	1
NGS211121-512	0		TPR exon21-NTRK1 exon12	34.15068493	Female	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS210520-212	1	.		57.40821918	Female	PTC	1b	1b	1
NGS211028-504	1	.		30.12054795	Female	PTC	1b	1b	1
NGS210713-506	1	.		26.40273973	Male	PTC	1a	1b	0
NGS210611-206	0	.		12.1260274	Male	PTC	4a	1	1
NGS210801-512	0	.		20.50410959	Male	PTC	3b	1b	0
NGS210322-206	0	.		31.9369863	Female	PTC	1b	0	1
NGS210904-501	0	.		60.01643836	Female	PTC	4a	1b	0
NGS210928-501	1	.		59.63013699	Male	FTC	3b	0	1
NGS210507-107	0	.		9.58630137	Male	PTC	1a	1b	0
NGS210823-507	1	.		37.66575342	Female	PTC	3b	1	1
NGS210313-201	0	.		55.03013699	Male	PTC	1a	1b	0
NGS210702-502	1	.		42.13424658	Male	PTC	4b	1b	1
NGS210205-088	0	.		21.4739726	Male	PTC	2	1b	0
NGS210329-113	1	.		48.66027397	Male	PTC	2	1b	1
NGS210315-205	0	.		46.26027397	Female	PTC	1b	1b	0
NGS211220-506	1	.		55.3369863	Male	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS210713-501	0	.		19.31232877	Female	PTC	1a	1b	1
NGS210605-201	0	.		6.660273973	Female	PTC	1b	1b	0

NGS210713-509	0	.	5.728767123	Male	PTC	4a	1b	0
NGS201223-071	1	.	31.6739726	Female	PTC	4a	1b	0
NGS201228-064	1	.	61.86027397	Female	PTC	1b	1b	0
NGS210507-104	1	.	56.1260274	Female	PTC	2	1b	1
NGS211205-525	1	TRIM33 exon12-NTRK1 exon13	51.32054795	Female	PTC	2	1b	1
NGS210928-509	1	.	38.43561644	Female	FTC	4a	1b	1
NGS211220-523	0	.	14.07945205	Female	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS211121-501	0	.	34.25479452	Female	PTC	1a	1b	1
NGS210329-105	1	.	44.70958904	Male	PTC	2	1b	1
NGS210210-073	0	.	45.66575342	Female	PTC	1a	1b	0
NGS210713-502	0	.	30.16712329	Female	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS210507-106	1	.	57.56712329	Female	PTC	4a	0	1
NGS220130-505	0	.	34.99178082	Female	PTC	3b	1b	1
NGS211024-514	1	.	35.96164384	Male	PTC	4b	1b	1
NGS211121-519	0	.	17.63287671	Female	PTC	na	1b	1
NGS210724-505	0	.	20.54520548	Male	PTC	3a	1b	1
NGS201223-073	1	.	48.88219178	Male	PTC	4b	1b	1
NGS210205-084	0	.	12.96712329	Female	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS211024-511	0	.	17.26027397	Female	PTC	3a	1b	1
NGS210205-086	0	.	17.24109589	Male	PTC	na	1a	1
NGS210808-503	0	.	14.53150685	Female	PTC	1b	1b	0
NGS210808-505	0	.	47.14794521	Male	PTC	1a	1b	1
NGS210117-130	0	.	53.27671233	Male	PTC	2	1b	1
NGS210808-502	0	.	46.50958904	Female	PTC	1b	1b	0
NGS210928-503	0	.	31.15068493	Female	PTC	1a	1b	1
NGS201228-065	0	.	24.6	Female	PTC	1b	1b	0
NGS210329-114	0	.	31.23287671	Male	PTC	2	1b	0
NGS210322-205	0	TPR exon21-TPR exon45-NTRK1 exon8	18.95890411	Female	PTC	3a	1b	1
NGS211205-513	1	.	35.2739726	Male	PTC	1b	1	1
NGS210313-203	0	.	29.37808219	Male	PTC	2	1b	1
NGS210814-503	0	.	15.12328767	Female	PTC	1b	1b	1
NGS210624-204	0	.	13.48767123	Female	PTC	1b	1b	1
NGS210525-208	0	.	49.75890411	Female	FTC	2	0	1
NGS210205-083	1	.	62.54246575	Female	FTC	x	1a	1

NGS210210-070	0	.	62.34794521	Female	PTC	1b	1b	0
NGS210808-507	0	.	32.71780822	Male	PTC	4a	1b	0
NGS210724-504	0	.	4.673972603	Male	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS210205-085	1	.	22.05205479	Male	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS210329-123	1	.	46.11232877	Male	PTC	1b	1b	0
NGS210808-506	1	.	11.2630137	Female	PTC	1b	1b	1
NGS210313-206	0	.	56.2	Male	FTC	1a	0	1
NGS201223-061	1	.	46.94246575	Female	PTC	2	1b	1
NGS201223-060	0	.	33.71780822	Female	PTC	4a	na	0
NGS210724-513	0	.	17.91506849	Female	PTC	1b	1b	0
NGS210329-111	1	.	67.78356164	Male	PTC	4b	1b	1
NGS211205-526	1	.	56.56986301	Male	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS210702-504	0	.	8.106849315	Female	PTC	2	1b	0
NGS201223-062	0	.	37.41917808	Male	PTC	1a	1b	0
NGS210713-510	0	.	29.98082192	Female	PTC	1b	1b	1
NGS210329-104	1	.	45.97534247	Female	PDTC	4a	0	1
NGS210713-508	0	.	7.378082192	Female	PTC	2	1b	1
NGS210814-502	0	STRN exon3-ALK exon20	17.10410959	Female	PTC	na	1b	1
NGS211231-516	0	.	33.55890411	Female	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS211024-507	0	.	19.16712329	Male	PTC	1b	1b	0
NGS210205-087	0	.	8.347945205	Female	Others	x	0	0
NGS220130-513	0	STRN exon3-ALK exon20	25.96438356	Female	PTC	2	1b	0
NGS211121-510	1	.	64.10958904	Female	PTC	4a	0	1
NGS201228-059	0	.	28.49041096	Male	PTC	1a	1b	0
NGS210405-205	1	.	57.36438356	Male	PTC	3b	1b	1
NGS220130-511	0	.	23.59178082	Male	PTC	3b	1b	1
NGS211205-512	1	.	34.76712329	Male	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS210928-504	0	.	18.69315068	Female	PTC	4a	1b	0
NGS220103-518	1	.	51.45479452	Female	PTC	3a	na	1
NGS210801-505	1	.	31.63835616	Female	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS210117-131	0	.	59.47123288	Female	PTC	2	1b	0
NGS201228-063	0	.	21.83287671	Female	PTC	1a	1b	1
NGS210713-505	0	.	48.59452055	Female	PTC	1a	1b	1
NGS210624-208	0	.	11.98082192	Male	PTC	2	1a	1
NGS220103-505	0	.	37.50410959	Male	PTC	3b	1b	0

NGS210117-136	1	.		30.16438356	Male	PTC	4b	1b	1
NGS210605-202	0	.		48.05205479	Female	PTC	3b	1b	0
NGS211231-508	0	.		20.24383562	Male	PTC	1b	1b	0
NGS210322-202	1	.		52.77534247	Female	PTC	2	1a	1
NGS211205-516	1	.		57.52876712	Male	PTC	3b	1b	1
NGS210529-109	0	.		61.89315068	Female	PTC	2	0	1
NGS211121-511	0	.		30.54794521	Female	PTC	1b	1b	0
NGS210823-508	1	.		57.11506849	Female	PTC	2	1b	1
NGS210329-101	1	.		20.76164384	Male	PTC	4b	1b	1
NGS210117-134	1		TPR exon21-NTRK1 exon12	23.08493151	Female	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS210928-513	0	.		21.61917808	Female	PTC	1a	1b	0
NGS210808-510	1	.		31.03835616	Male	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS210322-201	0	.		29.55616438	Female	PTC	1b	1b	1
NGS210210-072	0	.		11.6109589	Female	PTC	na	1b	1
NGS201223-059	0	.		33.87945205	Female	PTC	na	1b	1
NGS211231-520	1	.		34.8	Female	PTC	1a	1b	0
NGS210928-506	0	.		40.74520548	Female	PTC	1b	na	1
NGS211220-511	1	.		44.17260274	Female	PTC	1a	1b	1
NGS210411-200	0	.		33.76164384	Female	PTC	3b	1b	0
NGS220103-508	1	.		52.25753425	Female	PTC	4a	na	1
NGS210713-507	0	.		44.77534247	Female	PTC	3b	1b	0
NGS211121-525	0	.		25.59726027	Female	PTC	4b	1b	1
NGS220103-504	1	.		28.24383562	Female	PTC	1b	1	1
NGS211121-518	1	.		35.11780822	Female	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS210507-102	1	.		21.35342466	Female	PTC	na	na	1
NGS220103-509	1	.		60.57534247	Female	PTC	4a	0	1
NGS211205-514	1	.		67.33150685	Male	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS211121-517	1	.		67.03287671	Male	PTC	4a	1a	1
NGS210520-207	1	.		49.23561644	Male	PTC	1b	1b	1
NGS210713-503	1		STRN exon3-ALK exon20	8.591780822	Female	FTC	na	1	1
NGS211028-505	0	.		41.77260274	Female	PTC	1b	1b	1
NGS211121-526	0	.		33.87945205	Female	PTC	2	1b	1
NGS210624-210	0	.		28.59178082	Male	PTC	2	1b	1
NGS210801-501	1	.		31.84109589	Female	PTC	1a	1b	1
NGS211121-502	1	.		49.90410959	Female	PTC	4a	1b	1

NGS211121-506	1	.	49.26575342	Male	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS201228-062	1	.	59.34246575	Female	PTC	2	1b	1
NGS211028-518	0	SQSTM1 exon5-NTRK1 exon9	31.49863014	Female	PTC	1a	1b	1
NGS211220-509	1	.	16.74246575	Female	PTC	2	1b	1
NGS201223-058	0	.	27.68493151	Female	PTC	4a	1b	0
NGS210322-203	1	.	60.77260274	Female	PTC	3a	0	1
NGS210117-129	0	.	26.93972603	Male	PTC	1a	1b	0
NGS211028-506	1	.	47.90136986	Female	PTC	4b	1b	1
NGS210520-208	0	.	14.18082192	Female	PTC	2	1b	0
NGS210525-202	1	.	53.16438356	Female	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS220103-507	1	.	58.80547945	Male	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS211028-509	1	.	40.1260274	Male	PTC	1a	1a	1
NGS220130-508	1	.	38.81369863	Female	PTC	1b	1b	1
NGS210928-524	0	.	24.12054795	Female	PTC	2	1b	0
NGS210329-118	1	.	36.54520548	Male	PDTC	2	1b	1
NGS211220-524	0	.	29.09863014	Male	PTC	1b	1b	0
NGS211028-510	1	.	35.39178082	Male	PTC	1b	1b	1
NGS201228-067	1	.	54.43835616	Male	FTC	2	na	1
NGS210405-202	0	.	54.3890411	Female	FTC	3a	0	1
NGS210313-202	0	.	52.81917808	Female	PTC	1a	1a	1
NGS210724-503	0	.	26.33424658	Male	PTC	1b	1b	1
NGS210507-103	1	.	60.94520548	Female	PTC	1a	1b	1
NGS211121-505	0	.	8.367123288	Female	PTC	3a	1b	1
NGS210702-508	1	.	50.6630137	Male	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS210303-034	1	.	54.20273973	Male	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS211121-516	1	.	60.64657534	Male	PTC	2	1b	1
NGS210520-201	0	.	17.38356164	Male	PTC	3	1b	0
NGS210713-504	0	.	51.9890411	Female	PTC	3a	0	1
NGS201223-056	0	.	27.96164384	Female	PTC	3b	1b	0
NGS211028-501	0	.	18.52328767	Female	PTC	1a	1b	0
NGS210928-510	1	.	37.6630137	Male	PTC	3b	1b	1
NGS211205-517	1	.	36.61917808	Female	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS211024-515	0	.	37.89041096	Female	PTC	1b	1a	1
NGS201223-070	0	.	28.59726027	Female	PTC	4a	1a	1
NGS210724-501	0	.	36.08493151	Female	PTC	3a	1b	1

NGS211024-506	1	.		28.9260274	Female	PTC	na	na	1
NGS210928-517	1	.		58.84931507	Female	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS211024-509	0	.		18.23287671	Female	PTC	1b	1b	0
NGS210702-506	1	.		44.10958904	Male	PTC	3a	1b	0
NGS201228-068	0	.		18.12328767	Female	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS210525-207	1		TFG exon4-NTRK1 exon9	9.145205479	Female	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS210117-133	0	.		28.97808219	Male	PTC	4a	1b	0
NGS210823-505	1	.		60.56986301	Male	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS210329-120	0	.		46.44657534	Female	PTC	3b	0	1
NGS210928-514	0	.		54.86575342	Female	PTC	3b	1b	1
NGS211028-517	1	.		52.07945205	Female	PDTC	3a	1b	1
NGS211231-519	0	.		35.25479452	Female	PTC	2	1b	1
NGS210928-508	0	.		35.54794521	Female	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS211024-501	1	.		36.48767123	Female	PTC	3b	1a	1
NGS211205-507	0	.		41.97534247	Female	PTC	1a	1b	0
NGS210329-121	1	.		48.6630137	Female	PTC	na	na	1
NGS201228-066	1	.		36.70136986	Female	PTC	na	1b	1
NGS210520-204	1	.		54.12054795	Male	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS211024-504	0		STRN exon3-ALK exon20	9.876712329	Female	PTC	2	1b	1
NGS211231-512	1	.		27.52054795	Male	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS210724-507	0		TPR exon21-NTRK1 exon12	25.90684932	Male	PTC	3b	1b	1
NGS210808-512	1	.		16.86575342	Male	PTC	4b	1b	1
NGS210904-503	0	.		69.96164384	Male	PTC	x	0	1
NGS201223-072	0	.		31.52054795	Male	PTC	4a	1b	0
NGS211220-507	0	.		35.85479452	Male	PTC	1a	1b	1
NGS201223-076	1		NCOA4 exon6-RET exon11	23.37808219	Male	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS210411-201	0		PRKG1 exon2-RET exon12	41.83561644	Female	PTC	4a	1b	1
NGS210611-205	0		CCDC6 exon1-RET exon12	31.61369863	Female	PTC	1b	1b	1

Table S2. Sequencing Coverage and Quality Statistics of Targeted NGS.

Sample ID	Total number of sequenced reads	Total number of uniquely mapped non-duplicate reads ^{a,b}	Total number of covered targeted bases	Median coverage (and range) per targeted base	Percentage of targeted bases with coverage ≥ 200
NGS201223-058	4321991	2167022	450786600	2450 (0-11610)	78.21%
NGS201223-059	4255136	2847362	366599250	2009 (0-8794)	78.30%
NGS201223-	4607946	1982685	377230350	1629 (0-8352)	77.78%

060					
NGS201223-061	4421230	2461764	352606500	1058 (0-25511)	77.60%
NGS201223-062	4288727	2450693	425421150	2304 (0-9084)	77.97%
NGS201223-063	5420307	3251989	486675450	2654 (0-9695)	78.21%
NGS201223-064	4145129	2807379	375394350	2151 (0-8981)	78.22%
NGS201223-065	3894122	2280368	370621500	1736 (0-14850)	77.97%
NGS201223-070	4893528	1858172	520410150	2472 (0-20864)	78.24%
NGS201223-071	3777852	2481240	349810500	1993 (0-8638)	78.14%
NGS201223-072	3746372	2674595	391116000	2324 (0-8506)	78.23%
NGS201223-073	3800818	2563730	366088050	2068 (0-8226)	77.93%
NGS201223-074	4198031	2678082	244693350	1278 (0-9284)	78.03%
NGS201223-075	3493683	2369211	349003350	2101 (0-6718)	78.02%
NGS201223-076	3377126	2246805	174883350	774 (0-9919)	77.20%
NGS201223-077	3852813	2554911	396622200	2281 (0-7783)	78.22%
NGS201228-059	3044771	2409755	299825100	1422 (0-9566)	77.63%
NGS201228-060	3854408	3113963	367796550	2109 (0-6304)	77.89%
NGS201228-061	4182091	3181245	423760950	2270 (0-9242)	77.81%
NGS201228-062	3646013	2831976	326972550	1581 (0-7253)	77.77%
NGS201228-063	4138382	2404112	366939000	1521 (0-11422)	77.46%
NGS201228-064	3572764	2211031	285998250	1303 (0-5910)	77.55%
NGS201228-065	3406973	2745364	302562300	1537 (0-6610)	77.47%
NGS201228-066	5185158	2240658	447584850	1726 (0-16885)	77.88%
NGS201228-067	3154885	2038509	255245700	1165 (0-9744)	77.60%
NGS201228-068	3377006	2670391	332747700	1892 (0-5260)	77.77%
NGS210117-129	2871636	2476062	206700750	1172 (0-4409)	77.84%
NGS210117-130	3049675	2388645	199356600	991 (0-4248)	77.28%
NGS210117-131	2702806	2354057	137613300	738 (0-3896)	76.94%

NGS210117-133	1501559	1167236	72240900	341 (0-2959)	71.45%
NGS210117-134	2684644	2313515	119780700	582 (0-2705)	74.82%
NGS210117-135	2103294	1497321	87969600	458 (0-2029)	72.80%
NGS210117-136	2625411	2045837	128314950	589 (0-2579)	74.74%
NGS210117-138	3203178	2589393	135699600	726 (0-3817)	76.64%
NGS210205-080	4219688	3224745	338434350	1734 (0-6289)	99.07%
NGS210205-083	3773748	2902574	312702150	1630 (0-5972)	99.03%
NGS210205-084	4440928	3395954	393240900	2091 (0-6466)	99.38%
NGS210205-085	4526487	3416189	350945100	1735 (0-7521)	98.98%
NGS210205-086	4760133	3823401	361314450	1864 (0-5665)	99.11%
NGS210205-087	3865520	2204273	321048900	1474 (0-5863)	96.25%
NGS210205-088	4472832	3257285	397368900	1922 (0-16279)	99.24%
NGS210210-070	4184480	2315499	426090750	2155 (14-7009)	99.65%
NGS210210-071	3712788	1958208	304559400	1493 (0-7498)	98.83%
NGS210210-072	4072052	2189250	381734550	1891 (0-8033)	99.59%
NGS210210-073	5903247	3042433	557113800	2829 (0-9623)	99.70%
NGS210303-033	3267264	1840456	181855350	580 (3-3708)	87.51%
NGS210303-034	3520966	2080849	282688950	1251 (0-3864)	97.66%
NGS210313-201	6503875	3561460	325821150	1153 (0-16865)	96.32%
NGS210313-202	5810323	3489914	597660300	3289 (0-8447)	99.59%
NGS210313-203	9127526	3186155	761834250	3045 (21-11498)	99.71%
NGS210313-204	5213853	3166067	470442000	2408 (0-9365)	99.45%
NGS210313-205	7178032	3274107	614450850	2714 (10-10765)	99.59%
NGS210313-206	6609237	4045205	660475650	3606 (0-12050)	99.62%
NGS210315-203	4670509	3033517	450014550	2334 (13-7389)	99.41%
NGS210315-204	4947827	3359612	467105550	2400 (39-6863)	99.72%
NGS210315-	4880655	3046580	438472950	2234 (10-6153)	99.41%

205					
NGS210315-206	4886077	3054214	430932600	2084 (6-6026)	99.36%
NGS210322-201	4325661	2325238	356589900	1554 (15-5614)	99.13%
NGS210322-202	2883586	1921686	269621250	1440 (0-3993)	99.17%
NGS210322-203	4283879	2917692	246713850	1266 (50-4921)	98.56%
NGS210322-205	3880633	2321651	265849350	1304 (25-5413)	98.78%
NGS210322-207	4185683	2962433	46763400	106 (0-4644)	19.58%
NGS210329-101	5096087	3776836	460104750	2261 (0-10316)	99.34%
NGS210329-103	4710411	3468594	457989150	2373 (0-7210)	99.46%
NGS210329-104	6460211	4645700	328126500	1178 (0-6243)	97.29%
NGS210329-105	4674592	3395061	445239300	2388 (0-7308)	99.32%
NGS210329-111	4949241	3444977	492073650	2587 (0-6731)	99.50%
NGS210329-113	5265875	2642750	536794200	2343 (0-12164)	99.27%
NGS210329-114	3588782	2945686	215257050	1031 (0-6527)	96.69%
NGS210329-115	4592056	3483729	455724000	2512 (49-6553)	99.69%
NGS210329-118	5682314	1904216	589622550	2680 (0-9168)	99.43%
NGS210329-119	4035767	3107812	376938750	1999 (20-6622)	99.35%
NGS210329-120	5248988	4250292	618275700	3378 (2-23223)	99.61%
NGS210329-121	4032255	2678205	475171800	2431 (16-24919)	99.19%
NGS210329-123	4491467	3160386	503145750	2640 (0-15386)	99.33%
NGS210405-202	4099527	3370360	395559900	2122 (0-7325)	99.41%
NGS210405-205	4982038	3006886	442491450	1990 (7-12652)	99.49%
NGS210411-200	3932959	3295676	327396900	1724 (0-7150)	99.00%
NGS210411-201	4010763	2989256	349659150	1721 (0-6734)	98.83%
NGS210419-102	4207182	2638876	415485300	2169 (48-6077)	99.81%
NGS210507-100	4306016	3473447	379877700	2102 (0-5121)	99.25%
NGS210507-102	5327836	3009242	480192600	2405 (14-7394)	99.61%

NGS210507-103	5282786	4430956	514762650	2999 (0-7859)	99.67%
NGS210507-104	5353086	3384278	419121300	1907 (0-6154)	99.07%
NGS210507-106	5085038	3200102	522024600	2629 (0-8921)	99.38%
NGS210507-107	5136146	4092411	480738900	2677 (0-7494)	99.36%
NGS210520-201	3252099	2618100	352335600	1937 (0-4878)	99.50%
NGS210520-202	3273428	2648962	379858200	2071 (0-5428)	99.18%
NGS210520-203	5708349	3272383	601935000	2770 (0-9572)	99.65%
NGS210520-204	5969270	3187879	632680200	2810 (0-10932)	99.65%
NGS210520-206	3560442	2758512	374784450	2026 (0-5333)	99.47%
NGS210520-207	6283698	2338906	594493950	2503 (30-7721)	99.47%
NGS210520-208	2737164	2197197	291217950	1639 (0-4183)	99.15%
NGS210520-212	6553661	2380569	701672700	3005 (22-10849)	99.68%
NGS210525-202	3388760	2485375	398135550	1985 (0-6489)	99.25%
NGS210525-205	5457716	3307263	506362950	2032 (0-11760)	99.47%
NGS210525-207	3114820	2471660	289609500	1527 (0-4270)	98.82%
NGS210525-208	2808491	1898445	307044750	1343 (0-6046)	99.00%
NGS210529-109	4645016	3128169	503627550	2200 (50-11396)	99.78%
NGS210605-201	7333152	4298840	762263100	3789 (0-10970)	99.80%
NGS210605-202	6358801	3806710	633279000	3066 (86-10908)	99.92%
NGS210605-206	8227111	3331726	553229550	1595 (0-43683)	98.86%
NGS210624-204	9448399	4303330	1082713650	5421 (2-18514)	99.78%
NGS210624-205	10490214	4012694	1002097650	4378 (0-15320)	99.51%
NGS210624-208	4571385	3569019	495206850	2437 (61-11070)	99.77%
NGS210624-210	10193981	6226920	1214787300	6886 (0-15854)	99.82%
NGS210702-501	9484776	3134279	1026237750	4615 (0-17208)	99.52%
NGS210702-502	8448854	2802165	902391600	3901 (0-15534)	99.67%
NGS210702-	4185616	2533661	422454150	1851 (0-9121)	99.41%

503					
NGS210702-504	4227210	3204664	464885850	2247 (0-9054)	99.68%
NGS210702-505	3726538	2777426	393442800	1269 (30-11705)	99.15%
NGS210702-506	4654607	2793515	546213750	2512 (0-10078)	99.41%
NGS210702-508	2114026	392021	214135500	432 (0-18279)	78.39%
NGS210713-501	6191280	3775880	588951300	2048 (0-16757)	99.74%
NGS210713-502	6827290	3753041	629278500	2706 (0-13028)	99.70%
NGS210713-503	7145847	3968894	801325800	3948 (0-13550)	99.75%
NGS210713-504	7062100	4503950	666484050	3337 (0-14025)	99.73%
NGS210713-505	5646562	3572332	526764600	2744 (0-9388)	99.70%
NGS210713-506	6461455	4134517	733272300	3530 (0-14317)	99.71%
NGS210713-507	7885525	5906534	89095200	408 (0-1451)	83.03%
NGS210713-508	7371843	4518546	658760550	3301 (0-11045)	99.70%
NGS210713-509	7565126	5058113	531828150	2506 (0-12256)	99.61%
NGS210713-510	11496733	4374901	779013450	3475 (154-24865)	99.99%
NGS210801-501	14722259	3457681	1620328650	6308 (6-281282)	99.82%
NGS210801-504	7324784	3034958	810050700	3335 (0-81793)	99.79%
NGS210801-505	6008206	3625345	665613150	2842 (0-14127)	99.94%
NGS210801-509	6348188	3763787	746791050	3745 (0-16471)	99.63%
NGS211024-509	4507220	3454118	454161450	2274 (0-8476)	99.70%
NGS211024-511	4423395	3025193	510956400	2938 (0-8684)	99.58%
NGS211024-514	10060529	4034517	1210632300	6142 (0-22509)	99.83%
NGS211024-515	11212573	3940377	1241105550	6722 (0-19123)	99.82%
NGS211028-505	8458645	1299982	955123650	3402 (37-51972)	99.61%
NGS211028-506	32688095	5657029	2927253150	11371 (65-59818)	99.93%
NGS210611-207	6251800	3322418	678786750	3314 (0-12012)	99.62%
NGS210801-510	6792292	2068175	714553500	3431 (90-79718)	99.95%

NGS210801-511	6085565	3587840	703933050	3709 (0-14162)	99.84%
NGS210814-501	4719177	3676610	518499450	2957 (0-10113)	99.58%
NGS210814-502	10159538	2157821	1111645650	4652 (45-34558)	99.86%
NGS210814-503	8643056	3745419	833253600	3949 (0-33227)	99.79%
NGS210904-503	9484545	4498897	1044537450	5591 (0-19505)	99.79%
NGS210904-505	19822771	5842802	2029194900	9231 (0-43515)	99.79%
NGS210904-506	4637424	1900448	529274400	2794 (0-9302)	99.55%
NGS210904-510	9090277	4601164	1010947350	4880 (0-21723)	99.85%
NGS211024-501	8126270	3599606	744056850	3582 (51-19867)	99.94%
NGS211024-502	5010130	3230357	595800450	3368 (0-7512)	99.55%
NGS211024-504	4970704	2934385	573579300	3178 (56-10950)	99.83%
NGS211024-506	12292475	3361364	1392090600	6456 (86-21024)	99.95%
NGS211024-507	4899903	3157343	569578500	3184 (0-10928)	99.68%
NGS211024-512	4180369	3160891	432425250	2396 (0-9753)	99.43%
NGS211024-513	11519926	2593121	1310014950	6559 (0-20477)	99.63%
NGS211028-501	6485405	3897460	674459700	3617 (116-14854)	99.99%
NGS211028-503	6494978	3496732	665453850	3508 (0-9901)	99.78%
NGS211028-509	6890584	3462219	739890750	3927 (85-10660)	99.98%
NGS211028-510	6704290	3097272	660709050	3237 (0-10652)	99.60%
NGS211028-517	7711556	3677390	809562300	4033 (0-14690)	99.78%
NGS211028-518	15636700	4013414	1769889150	8110 (138-23912)	100.00%
NGS211121-502	14891284	2703414	752868900	1837 (0-45482)	98.42%
NGS211121-525	4952433	4262311	473694750	2540 (0-7792)	99.63%
NGS211121-526	5436306	3233216	466738950	2138 (9-7054)	99.55%
NGS211205-505	39464126	4927080	4283039400	16265 (0-79590)	99.88%
NGS211205-507	7949485	3993150	885446700	4477 (0-16413)	99.78%
NGS211205-	9585713	4976817	1025096700	5282 (0-20126)	99.79%

508					
NGS211205-509	35539589	2958293	3879585600	17555 (0-65938)	99.83%
NGS211205-511	9018933	4391277	1015878600	5223 (0-19235)	99.78%
NGS211205-512	9953577	4586287	965329350	4695 (144-20096)	100.00%
NGS211205-513	8672442	3781429	874914900	3534 (4-29108)	99.83%
NGS211205-514	7747958	4450533	850326000	4190 (0-19323)	99.85%
NGS211205-515	10701134	5534252	1231494150	6746 (0-20300)	99.85%
NGS211205-516	7803927	3256893	910697700	3815 (172-19227)	100.00%
NGS211205-517	9404681	3342885	855793500	3825 (0-22263)	99.63%
NGS211205-522	3309756	1724320	358022700	1968 (0-7409)	99.06%
NGS211205-525	4386729	3136205	407977950	2163 (0-8003)	99.48%
NGS211205-526	3811254	2637960	291621600	1054 (0-12693)	96.82%
NGS211220-506	6564119	4027251	555682200	2931 (0-13155)	99.75%
NGS211220-507	6775460	2755255	745271700	3834 (4-15362)	99.63%
NGS211220-509	6019509	3501172	566311050	3012 (0-13285)	99.77%
NGS211220-511	7210173	3640824	734117700	3902 (8-11597)	99.77%
NGS211220-513	7849433	3712547	856572750	4519 (0-11641)	99.84%
NGS211220-515	6256594	3342073	591049350	3050 (70-12179)	99.95%
NGS211220-517	7061306	3279775	589245600	2516 (0-23903)	99.59%
NGS211220-518	10359396	4531399	863557050	4217 (0-19286)	99.85%
NGS211220-520	14070127	4155240	1512158550	6995 (0-51520)	99.79%
NGS211220-523	3956906	2650352	389213850	2209 (0-7332)	99.78%
NGS211220-524	8860586	4069892	744459900	2863 (0-20552)	99.80%
NGS210611-206	6717873	3019375	679633350	3102 (56-13182)	99.93%
NGS210611-205	17647742	1430629	1954363200	9253 (245-46021)	100.00%
NGS210322-206	2964464	2054233	190240200	981 (0-4404)	96.46%
NGS210405-201	5066580	3091768	388670550	1652 (0-7789)	98.97%

NGS210611-201	54991139	6992377	6334998600	30221 (952-178754)	100.00%
NGS210724-501	4342994	2558135	499700850	2321 (0-12044)	99.36%
NGS210724-504	4834069	2972461	580039950	2794 (0-12781)	99.40%
NGS210724-503	5127302	3496679	580912350	2551 (36-18519)	99.78%
NGS210724-505	4312155	2219264	519842850	1952 (0-17431)	99.13%
NGS210724-506	4440112	2635454	528948900	2175 (0-17298)	99.33%
NGS210724-513	5211545	3625278	595690950	2488 (21-19739)	99.75%
NGS210724-507	4629722	2948994	547857150	2305 (29-21007)	99.61%
NGS210724-514	4863578	2990004	559010850	2592 (0-14748)	99.47%
NGS210801-512	6301912	3649301	729357600	3612 (0-12441)	99.76%
NGS211028-507	6501412	3856514	711039000	4011 (124-11855)	99.99%
NGS211121-501	5659429	4182522	612357900	3723 (0-10162)	99.52%
NGS211121-505	7006598	2461520	778609350	3887 (0-18202)	99.72%
NGS211121-504	8507538	3447057	911208750	4994 (0-20179)	99.85%
NGS211121-507	5753286	2926159	618617250	3529 (0-12907)	99.80%
NGS211121-506	4489082	2357180	382771050	1704 (87-17510)	99.09%
NGS211121-511	5609725	3024119	634115400	3625 (0-13457)	99.73%
NGS211121-513	6993658	3704847	740797650	4124 (0-20440)	99.62%
NGS211121-516	6114216	2957899	584816850	3024 (0-13167)	99.77%
NGS211121-517	4098699	2699563	427611300	2476 (94-12409)	99.85%
NGS211121-518	6068558	3169913	593356650	2915 (0-30311)	99.57%
NGS211231-503	4784286	3766015	447448200	2431 (0-7645)	99.50%
NGS201223-056	3928679	2670276	390442950	2247 (0-7456)	78.16%
NGS210808-501	8025942	4380154	852483600	4757 (0-15326)	99.84%
NGS210808-503	6144786	3029149	603921900	2728 (0-41309)	99.63%
NGS210808-502	9304187	5177855	1019949450	5542 (0-18755)	99.79%
NGS210808-	7062944	4024901	750368400	3816 (101-	99.97%

504				27374)	
NGS210808-505	8045849	3478771	786212100	3952 (0-12785)	99.76%
NGS210808-506	7749243	3929853	770856150	3898 (0-13618)	99.60%
NGS210808-507	9220650	4574783	971913600	4995 (0-21026)	99.77%
NGS210808-508	7793248	4035444	826978650	4311 (0-16607)	99.64%
NGS210808-511	7236124	4481374	797268300	4517 (116-14418)	99.99%
NGS210808-510	9054317	3945744	966114750	4631 (0-21296)	99.80%
NGS210808-512	8262176	3864977	899497200	4926 (0-13458)	99.64%
NGS210823-504	3657209	2735012	421113450	2069 (0-11745)	99.09%
NGS210823-506	7140002	4995944	632274000	3179 (51-17334)	99.78%
NGS210823-505	9721512	3126680	967079850	4471 (42-23483)	99.81%
NGS210928-501	7213452	1091622	801856800	3168 (0-65644)	99.63%
NGS210823-507	7356168	4997657	796695000	4958 (0-11840)	99.79%
NGS210823-508	7114419	4769747	743050500	4112 (0-11997)	99.81%
NGS210823-509	7027331	2953753	489962400	1712 (0-22074)	98.79%
NGS210904-501	9166125	4419057	1053064800	5345 (0-22654)	99.64%
NGS210928-503	4344240	2538054	494126850	2639 (0-11197)	99.67%
NGS210928-504	6695760	4190313	726884700	2832 (0-31798)	99.77%
NGS210928-506	5755806	3545670	616052850	2917 (0-20584)	99.77%
NGS210928-507	7441382	4334522	864443850	4832 (0-21441)	99.82%
NGS210928-508	4461161	2230962	493090350	2356 (0-13721)	99.70%
NGS210928-509	5673883	2865763	667786050	3480 (0-16916)	99.73%
NGS210928-510	6746724	2470743	736404300	3429 (63-19418)	99.91%
NGS210928-515	3172232	1675963	372980850	2040 (0-7107)	99.29%
NGS210928-514	3849907	2273451	429552750	2283 (0-11603)	99.60%
NGS210928-513	10824339	3422103	1269553500	6969 (0-25370)	99.79%
NGS210928-517	4923696	2676582	572355450	3264 (0-11068)	99.72%

NGS210928-520	6936345	2139480	707911650	3013 (94-21814)	99.88%
NGS210928-522	8741817	3125565	990064500	4158 (132-29612)	99.96%
NGS210928-523	5756245	3133194	618648750	2366 (0-24664)	99.67%
NGS210928-524	6310649	3642300	710792850	4005 (0-15896)	99.70%
NGS211028-504	7339936	3540686	841487700	4030 (0-16230)	99.77%
NGS211121-510	5821089	3157826	587790300	2936 (88-27322)	99.79%
NGS211121-508	10465653	3666827	971624250	5149 (0-25071)	99.64%
NGS211121-515	4913865	2634674	542283000	3091 (0-11499)	99.69%
NGS211121-512	7537929	2354436	793973400	3890 (0-20203)	99.80%
NGS211231-501	4400683	3406042	488380500	2723 (0-8619)	99.45%
NGS211231-505	4876353	1579922	413436000	1832 (0-15266)	99.00%
NGS211231-508	4302179	3325757	466765650	2558 (0-9486)	99.60%
NGS211231-515	3700458	913834	409975200	1802 (16-13658)	99.09%
NGS211121-519	16385855	3622203	1683917400	8296 (160-35608)	99.98%
NGS211231-512	12664518	6224135	1391101200	7386 (0-28765)	99.63%
NGS220103-504	4257005	2889186	457438350	2428 (29-9056)	99.72%
NGS211231-520	8304255	2609760	973995600	3636 (0-29561)	99.36%
NGS211231-516	12785440	5064793	1386705750	8146 (234-29526)	100.00%
NGS211231-519	11931722	5981841	1265967750	6706 (0-35696)	99.98%
NGS220103-506	3388870	889152	290276250	1025 (0-10401)	93.12%
NGS220103-505	10541254	4347570	1203751800	6458 (0-39416)	99.64%
NGS220103-508	5401428	1585476	543931500	2658 (83-18892)	99.78%
NGS220103-509	4922940	2125590	399673650	1785 (49-11063)	98.95%
NGS220103-507	10783897	5061115	1222697100	7330 (0-24708)	99.64%
NGS220103-510	8391566	2782468	887442300	4143 (0-33247)	99.75%
NGS220103-513	7426914	2804873	861900450	4532 (0-24988)	99.76%
NGS220125-	4162964	2673341	439333050	2286 (0-7773)	99.59%

501					
NGS220103-518	7812295	2809744	655268850	2922 (0-21807)	99.56%
NGS220125-505	4562680	2733608	517738800	2702 (0-8054)	99.52%
NGS220125-507	4412581	3515972	498910500	2456 (0-9560)	99.53%
NGS220125-513	4121744	3072012	414227100	2377 (0-6373)	99.45%
NGS220130-505	5723289	3275254	524468700	2787 (0-11044)	99.82%
NGS220130-508	7119619	4337162	697504650	3262 (135-20479)	99.98%
NGS220130-511	8360178	4070485	948726450	5156 (109-15268)	100.00%
NGS220130-513	6676147	4196857	630288300	3387 (0-11641)	99.82%
NGS220130-510	7576423	3871601	626495850	2902 (0-16373)	99.76%
NGS220228-501	12618864	4584278	1332530850	6488 (165-25531)	100.00%

^aSpecify in table description or legend which reference genome was used (e.g., GRCh38).

^bIn case amplicon libraries are generated using multiplex PCR, then the “Total number of uniquely mapped reads” should be reported. Range is defined as the minimum – maximum coverage (e.g., Median coverage (and range): 221 (25-638)).

Table S3. Univariate and multivariate logistic regression analyses were used to evaluate the associations of N stage with the major genetic alterations.

Univariate logistic regression analysis					
Characteristics	P Value	OR	Lower	Upper	
Fusion oncogenes	0.008	15.467	2.069	115.647	
BRAF	0.14	1.859	0.816	4.235	
TERT	0.03	0.396	0.172	0.912	
TP53	0.299	0.495	0.131	1.867	
RAS	<0.0001	0.02	0.005	0.077	
Multivariate logistic regression analysis					
Fusion oncogenes	0.039	8.64	1.115	66.918	
TERT	0.508	0.709	0.255	1.966	
RAS	<0.0001	0.03	0.008	0.118	

Table S4. Difference in RAI-refractoriness between patients with RET-NCOA4 and patients with RET-CCDC6.

Pediatric Patients		
RET/PTC Type	RAI-refractoriness (Yes)	RAI-refractoriness (No)
RET-NCOA4	6 (54.5%)	5 (45.5%)
RET-CCDC6	2 (25%)	6 (75%)
Adult Patients		
RET-NCOA4	7 (33.3%)	14 (66.7%)
RET-CCDC6	7 (36.8%)	12 (63.2%)

Figure S1. Age of patients with RET-NCOA4 and patients with RET-CCDC6.

Figure S2. NIS expression between WT PTC, PTC with BRAF mutation, and PTC with fusions.

Figure S3. The proportion of RAI-refractoriness in the Fusions group and the TERT mutation group.

